

Responsible AI principles and the GLAM sector: an initial review

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Introduction

Increasing interest in, and deployment of, AI technologies has been accompanied by significant regulatory and research efforts focused on defining responsible use of AI. This document provides a summary of Responsible AI (RAI) principles and their application to Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (the GLAM sector). The purpose of providing this summary is to enable GLAM sector organisations to review and reflect on existing RAI principles and adapt them to their local context, mission, and needs. Principles such as Indigenous self-determination and data rights, and justice and fairness, will depend on local expertise (Berman and Smithies 2025).

Responsible AI principles

While responsible or ethical AI practices remain highly contested (Green 2021), from a policy perspective there is considerable consensus regarding the high-level ethical principles ('RAI principles') that responsible actors ought to attend to when researching, developing, or deploying an AI system. As Morley et al. (2020) highlight, a vast number of statements articulating RAI principles have been promulgated in recent years, by industry, government, and academic actors. Table 1 provides a summary of core RAI principles.

Jobin et al. (2019) conducted a scoping review of 84 of these statements, finding emerging convergence on the principles of *transparency*, *justice* and *fairness*, *non-maleficence*, *responsibility* and *privacy*. Khan et al. (2022), through a systematic literature review of RAI principles, find similar alignment around the principles of *transparency*, *privacy*, *accountability*, and *fairness*. Corrêa et al. (2023) also find that *transparency*, *reliability*, *justice* and *fairness*, *privacy*, *beneficence* and *non-maleficence*, *diversity*, and *accountability* are consistently addressed in RAI guidelines, although they highlight divergences in the extent to which guidelines address issues related to children, Intellectual Property, truthfulness, labor rights, sustainability, human-centeredness, open source, and human rights and dignity. Convergence around shared themes is unsurprising, given the high degree of cross-referencing across the statements produced by different actors (Schiff et al. 2020). These themes are also reflected in efforts to standardize AI governance (e.g., OECD 2025) in Europe, North America, and Asia (Morley et al. 2020), although it should be noted that Global Majority countries are significantly under-represented in AI governance discussions and efforts (Corrêa et al. 2023). Alignment of high-level ethical principles, however, should not be mistaken for consensus as to their operationalization or completeness. Statements of RAI principles may not be sufficiently grounded in a human rights framework (Fukuda-Parr and Gibbons 2021), or might obscure substantial differences in how questions of community participation and human-centered design should be applied to AI (Schiff 2025), or might be too high-level and leave unaddressed fundamental questions of implementation (Munn 2023).

Table 1. Summary of Responsible AI principles

Principle	Requirements for GLAM sector organisations
Transparency	Provide sufficient disclosure about an AI system's purpose, data, development, and limitations to enable appropriate understanding and oversight (Tabassi 2023). In relation to AI use with collections data, public documentation covering provenance, data transformations, rights, intended

	use cases and audiences, risks, constraints and restrictions on reuse (Alkemade et al. 2023; Candela et al. 2025; Lee 2025).
Accountability	Ensure accountability structures are in place, including clear roles and responsibilities for the governance of AI projects, and practices for ensuring traceability and answerability for AI use decisions (Manchester 2023; Padilla 2019; Tabassi 2023). Audit AI projects routinely to ensure alignment to RAI principles and institutional governance processes (Mannheimer et al. 2024; Saccucci and Potter 2024).
Accuracy	Ensure AI outputs are accurate, reliable, and fit-for-purpose. Measure and validate performance with domain-specific evaluation and clear thresholds for deployment (Heller 2024). Do not deploy AI when accuracy is insufficient for the defined use case (Anderson and Duran 2024; Bongini, Becattini, and Del Bimbo 2023; Saccucci and Potter 2024).
Justice and fairness	Ensure AI systems treat all stakeholders equitably (i.e. systems should not be biased or discriminatory) and address structural inequities (e.g. regarding digital divide and system access) (Mannheimer et al. 2024; Tabassi 2023). Champion fair and open use of collections (Association of Research Libraries 2024).
Privacy	Ensure that collection and retention of data is limited, and confidentiality is protected (Tabassi 2023). In relation to sensitive data within collections, ensure this is not included in model training and require vendors and service providers to respect privacy requirements (Hosseini et al. 2024; Mannheimer et al. 2024).
Beneficence	Ensure AI systems are beneficial to people and the environment (Morley et al. 2020). Evaluate and minimize environmental footprint of AI and align with institutional sustainability commitments (Heller 2024; Mannheimer et al. 2024; Strubell, Ganesh, and McCallum 2019).
Non-maleficence	Proactively reduce potential harms and negative impacts across the AI system lifecycle (Tabassi 2023), and ensure AI systems are robust and secure (Morley et al. 2020). Ensure human review is in place for AI use in sensitive tasks, such as document access decisions (Association of Research Libraries 2024).

Responsible AI principles in the GLAM sector

The principles of *transparency*, *justice* and *fairness*, *beneficence* and *non-maleficence*, *accountability* and *privacy* are reflected in emerging efforts from GLAM sector organisations to define their approaches to responsible AI use (e.g., Association of Research Libraries 2024; Dikow et al. 2023; Fitsilis, Lucke, and Vrieze 2024; National Library of Australia 2025; The National Archives 2024) and in GLAM sector scholarship on RAI (Mannheimer et al. 2024). Complementing these organisational efforts, recent scholarship in the European context has sought to design ethical frameworks specifically for AI use in cultural heritage. Pansoni et al. (2023) identify six ethical pitfalls associated with AI, proposing corresponding principles such as *shared responsibility* to counter the difficulty of attributing AI impacts, and *cultural continuity* to address historical biases. They also emphasize the centrality of physical spaces to counter the risk of AI deployments justifying the destruction of physical heritage. Building on this, Tiribelli et al. (2024) highlight that RAI efforts in the GLAM sector need to grapple with the potential for AI technologies to undermine authenticity, implement top-down universality approaches, and challenge existing concepts of authorship.

These efforts also extend RAI principles to address specific concerns of the GLAM sector. Table 2 highlights additional RAI principles that have been proposed for the GLAM sector. The authoritative role of GLAM sector organisations, in relation to stewardship of cultural knowledge, elevates and complicates questions of AI accuracy and bias, particularly when collections data may contain inaccuracies or biases (Anderson and Duran 2024; Mannheimer et al. 2024; Wolff, Sergeevna Mainzer, and Drummond 2024), and introduces new issues related to the potential to use AI technologies to justify the destruction of physical collections (Tiribelli et al. 2024). Similarly, issues of justice and fairness, particularly in relation to communities who are represented in collections and First Nations communities, are vitally important, particularly to GLAM sector organisations in post-colonial contexts (Dikow et al. 2023; Fitsilis et al. 2024; National Library of Australia 2025). And, as publicly funded organisations, issues of access to costly or online-only AI tools are also significant (Feng, Wang, and Anderson 2024; Mannheimer et al. 2024) and may disproportionately impact structurally marginalized communities.

The positioning of GLAM sector organisations as public organisations, often housed within government agencies, also elevates questions of legal and policy compliance. Legal compliance, in relation to ensuring AI models (and their training data) respect intellectual property (Fitsilis et al. 2024) and copyright law (National Library of Australia 2025), and policy compliance in relation to broader government AI guidelines, are therefore emphasized (National Library of Australia 2025; The National Archives 2024). Relatedly, issues of consent for using AI technologies with collections data are highlighted (Hosseini et al. 2024; Wolff et al. 2024). Finally, the need to account for the impact of AI adoption on GLAM sector staff (Anderson and Duran 2024; Mannheimer et al. 2024; McIrvine et al. 2024; Pastva et al. 2024) and the environment (Dikow et al. 2023) is highlighted. These are two needs which are particularly salient to GLAM sector organisations that are housed within the public sector and may therefore be required to comply to public sector employment processes and environmental impact requirements.

Table 2. Additional GLAM sector-specific Responsible AI principles

Principle	Requirements for GLAM sector organisations
Access	Ensure equitable and democratic (ideally free) access to AI-enabled services and provide public guidance and training on their use (Cordell 2020; Mannheimer et al. 2024; Pansoni et al. 2023); foster digital and AI literacy (Association of Research Libraries 2024).
Indigenous self-determination and data rights	Ensure Indigenous data sovereignty, control and ownership, and the right to self-determination is upheld in any project where First Nations knowledge or data is to be represented, used, or developed through AI (CARE Principles 2023). Co-develop AI practices with First Nations communities and build participatory governance and culturally appropriate workflows (Thorpe et al. 2021). Recognise and address harms caused to Indigenous peoples by failures by cultural sector organisations to uphold Indigenous rights (Thorpe 2024).
Consent	Obtain and document permission from rights-holders and communities. Do not assume that historical permission to collect data automatically implies consent to use of AI processes with collected data. For sensitive or community-held materials, implement consultation and advisory processes before AI use (Hosseini et al. 2024).

Legal and policy compliance	Ensure adherence to copyright, IP, licensing, and institutional and government policies relevant to AI projects and data reuse (Association of Research Libraries 2024; Heller 2024; Manchester 2023; Padilla 2019). Develop clear policies on how use of AI systems will be reflected in authorship and attribution metadata (Tiribelli et al. 2024). Articulate and track the rights, licenses, and restrictions in documentation of datasets (Alkemade et al. 2023; Candela et al. 2025), and align AI initiatives with organizational policy and governance expectations (National Library of Australia 2025; The National Archives 2024).
Respect for employees	Adopt AI in ways that support professional ethics, labour standards, and staff well-being, and contribute to workforce diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (Tabassi 2023). Center staff expertise in scoping and evaluation of AI projects and provide targeted upskilling resources and time (Darby et al. 2022; Padilla 2019). Integrate conservators and collection managers into AI planning and risk assessment (Jaillant et al. 2025; Rouhani 2023).
Responsibility for physical collections	Ensure AI augments, and does not replace, stewardship of material collections. Avoid digital substitution narratives that could justify neglect or destruction of physical records or cultural heritage (Tiribelli et al. 2024).

FAIR and CARE principles

As AI technologies are data technologies, and as GLAM sector organisations are stewards of scientific collections and collections that contain First Nations' cultural heritage, we note that the FAIR principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and the CARE principles for Indigenous data governance (CARE Principles 2023; Carroll et al. 2020) should also be incorporated in RAI principles for the GLAM sector. This is somewhat reflected in the principles listed in Table 2, above, but also warrants further explication. We note, also, that compatibility between FAIR and CARE principles should not be assumed, as there may be instances where FAIR principles undermine Indigenous peoples' authority to control how Indigenous data is shared. Table 3 below provides a summary of FAIR and CARE principles, and their application to AI technologies.

Table 3. FAIR and CARE principles

Principle	General requirements for GLAM sector organisations	Relevance to AI technologies
Findable	Research data, including GLAM collections, should be findable, meaning that they are associated with rich metadata and are indexed so as to be searchable (Wilkinson et al. 2016).	At a minimum, AI models should be findable, with unique identifiers linking to detailed information pertaining to the model weights and architecture, training data, and dependencies (Ravi et al. 2022). Similar findability requirements should apply to all other AI components, including training data, evaluation data, and model interfaces. AI-specific platforms for publishing AI models and components can aide in findability 12/1/2025 9:48:00 AM

Accessible	Research data should be accessible, meaning they can be retrieved using an open, free, universally implementable communications protocol (Wilkinson et al. 2016).	AI models and components, and their metadata, should be discoverable and freely downloadable or invoked (Ravi et al. 2022), e.g. through APIs and standard protocols for access (Radha, Kuehlkamp, and Nabrzyski 2025).
Interoperable	Research data should be interoperable, meaning that they use a common machine language and standard vocabularies, and necessary references to other data (Wilkinson et al. 2016).	AI models and components should be able to be used on disparate hardware, ideally through containerizing the system (Ravi et al. 2022), and AI models and components should not lock in users to particular hardware or paid services (Radha et al. 2025).
Reusable	Reuse of research data should be supported, through detailed attributions, clear licensing, use of relevant community standards (Wilkinson et al. 2016), and provision of instructions or tools to support data exploration and reuse (Ravi et al. 2022).	In addition to the usual reusability requirements, AI models and components should be published alongside quantifiable metrics that enable users to determine appropriate reuse of the model (Ravi et al. 2022), and to avoid unnecessary duplication of model training efforts (Radha et al. 2025).
Collective Benefit	Where Indigenous data is used or collected by GLAM organisations, it should result in tangible benefits for Indigenous communities, by enabling Indigenous communities to use and reuse this data (Carroll et al. 2020; O'Brien et al. 2024).	AI technologies can support the revitalization and maintenance of Indigenous languages and knowledge (Barrowcliffe et al. 2025), but collective benefit needs to be established at the level of, and with, local communities (Abdilla et al. 2020).
Authority to Control	Indigenous people must have authority to control Indigenous data, including authority to set data governance protocols, and access to data that is needed for Indigenous governance and self-determination (Carroll et al. 2020).	AI governance processes should not displace Indigenous governance and self-determination. Free, prior, and informed consent is necessary for use of Indigenous data in AI systems, and AI systems should have Indigenous protocols for access and control of Indigenous data built into them (Barrowcliffe et al. 2025). Indigenous communities should have authority to decide where Intellectual Property rights reside (Abdilla et al. 2020).
Responsibility	GLAM organisations have a responsibility to build respectful relationships with Indigenous peoples by sharing how Indigenous data is	Indigenous capabilities in AI should be developed through partnerships, capacity building, and AI literacy training (Barrowcliffe et al. 2025), and

	being used to enable collective benefits for Indigenous peoples, and investing in capacity development (Carroll et al. 2020; O'Brien et al. 2024).	AI projects that involve Indigenous data should be accountable to Indigenous communities (Abdilla et al. 2020).
Ethics	The rights and wellbeing of Indigenous peoples should be the primary concern in all stages of the data lifecycle, and Indigenous peoples should be empowered to assess benefits, harms, and potential future uses associated with Indigenous data (Carroll et al. 2020; O'Brien et al. 2024).	The rights and wellbeing of Indigenous peoples extends to their right to care for Country, meaning that Indigenous people should be empowered to assess the environmental impact of AI and all stages of the AI supply chain, alongside the potential for AI technologies to re-traumatise Indigenous people through racist AI outputs (Abdilla et al. 2020; Barrowcliffe et al. 2025).

Bringing it together: a synthesized set of Responsible AI principles for the GLAM sector

The preceding sections outlined many normative principles which GLAM sector organisations can use to inform their engagement with AI technologies. As may be expected, given the shared focus across these principles on AI or data technologies, there is substantial conceptual overlap across various principles. Accordingly, in Table 4 we provide a synthesis of the different principles outlined above. This synthesis can be used as a starting point for GLAM sector organisations to develop their own more detailed RAI principles and definition; individual principles are likely to have greater or lesser salience depending on the organisation, the AI technology, and the collection.

Table 4. Responsible AI principles for the GLAM sector

Themes	Integrated principles	Requirements for GLAM sector
1. Justice and fairness	Justice and fairness (Table 1), Indigenous self-determination (Table 2), Access (Table 2), Authority to Control (Table 3), Collective Benefit (Table 3)	AI systems used by GLAM sector organisations should treat all stakeholders equitably and should proactively address structural or historical inequities. Where GLAM sector organisations are considering using AI technologies in relation to Indigenous data or knowledge, such decisions and processes should uphold Indigenous peoples' right to self-determination and data sovereignty. Doing so requires grounded partnerships with relevant Indigenous communities, and support for Indigenous communities to set AI governance protocols and requirements.
2. Governance, consent, and accountability	Accountability (Table 1), Legal and policy compliance (Table 2),	When embarking on AI projects, GLAM sector organisations should establish clear governance processes, which enable

	Consent (Table 2), Responsibility for physical collections (Table 2), Responsibility (Table 3)	<p>traceability and accountability for AI decisions and ensure consent is obtained from data rights' holders for AI use. AI projects should be assessed with regards to relevant Copyright and Intellectual Property laws and institutional policies, and with regards to the risk of neglect or destruction of physical records and the potential cost of scaling AI technologies across GLAM sector collections.</p> <p>Where an AI project may involve Indigenous data, a prerequisite is respectful relationships with Indigenous peoples, based on investment in Indigenous peoples' AI capacity and shared understanding of potential benefits of the project. Historical collection permission should not be assumed to imply consent for use of Indigenous data in AI training.</p>
3. Transparency and openness	Transparency (Table 1), Findable (Table 3), Accessible (Table 3), Interoperable (Table 3), Reusable (Table 3)	<p>The use of AI systems and technologies by GLAM sector organisations should be transparently documented. System purpose, data provenance, data operations, system limitations, and system dependencies should be disclosed to users. AI models and other AI components used by GLAM sector organisations should be findable (with high quality metadata), accessible (via APIs and direct download of models and training data), interoperable (through containerization and the avoidance of proprietary AI products), and reusable (through clear licensing and documentation).</p> <p>Where an AI project may involve Indigenous data, the principle of openness should itself be subject of discussion and definition by Indigenous peoples'.</p>
4. Safety, privacy, and respect	Non-maleficence (Table 1), Privacy (Table 1), Ethics (Table 3)	<p>AI systems used by GLAM sector organisations should proactively address known limitations with AI technologies (i.e. hallucinations, discriminatory and harmful outputs), while respecting and protecting the data of system users. Data collection through AI systems should be limited and protect confidentiality.</p> <p>The potential for GLAM sector collections to be used in AI training, with or without institutional permission, should be carefully considered</p>

		<p>whenever collections are published or digitized. Collections' metadata should include clear guidance on appropriate use for model training. The potential for collections' to include harmful stereotypes, racist depictions, and other content that may be offensive should be considered, given the potential link between the inclusion of such data in AI training and the reproduction of such content by AI models.</p> <p>Indigenous peoples should be consulted and empowered to determine whether and how Indigenous data stewarded by GLAM sector organisations is allowed to be used for AI training.</p>
5. People and planet	Beneficence (Table 1), Respect for employees (Table 2)	<p>AI systems used by GLAM sector organisations should be fit-for-purpose, acknowledging the unique missions and responsibilities of the GLAM sector. Given the significant environmental impact of AI technologies, decisions to use AI technologies should be based on a clear assessment of their potential benefit to GLAM sector stakeholders and the communities GLAM sector organisations serve.</p> <p>The development and deployment of AI systems should aim to empower and strengthen the capacity and expertise of GLAM practitioners, rather than displace GLAM practitioners.</p>
6. Accuracy and authenticity	Accuracy (Table 1)	<p>Given the unique authoritative voice of GLAM sector organisations, the accuracy of any AI system that may speak on behalf of a GLAM sector organisation needs to be thoroughly considered. Doing so may require development of collections- or organisational-specific definitions of accuracy, and collections-specific evaluations of the authenticity of AI model outputs.</p> <p>The potential for disparate AI system performance (i.e. for AI systems to perform less well on data that is sparsely represented within collections), and the additional potential for patterns of disparate AI system performance to replicate historical patterns of</p>

	marginalization should be considered when evaluating AI systems for use in GLAM sector organisations.
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